

RESEARCH TO PROPOSE SOLUTIONS TO ENCOURAGE AND PROMOTE PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) MODELS IN DEVELOPING TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION PROJECTS IN VIETNAM

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Problem

Public-Private Partnership (PPP) is an attractive model for implementing projects in general and, specifically, science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam today. However, in reality, PPP projects in the field of science, technology, and innovation in Vietnam are still very limited, and there are almost no large-scale projects. When it comes to PPP in activities related to science, technology, and innovation, enterprises are often hesitant and unclear about how to proceed. Many questions need to be answered regarding legal mechanisms, implementation frameworks, methods of collaboration, delineation of outputs, responsibilities of the parties, and evaluation of the effectiveness of science, technology, and innovation products. These analyses clearly show the need for specific research on PPP models in implementing science, technology, and innovation projects in the current context in Vietnam. Consideration should be given to offering some suggestions to improve quality and promote PPP activities during the implementation of these projects.

Scientific, technological, and innovative activities have unique characteristics related to cost calculation methods, project organization, efficiency analysis, evaluation of project outcomes, risk management, and social impact analysis. Therefore, when implementing science, technology, and innovation projects in the form of Public-Private Partnerships (PPP), many different questions arise. Certain specific aspects of Vietnamese policies, especially those related to public assets and intellectual property, also pose challenges. Thus, researching the application of PPP models in the implementation of science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam is very interesting, with many findings, but also very challenging.

PURPOSE

- + Provide theoretical and practical foundations for solutions to encourage and promote the PPP model in the provision of Science, Technology, and Innovation projects in Vietnam.
- + Propose solutions to encourage and promote the PPP model in the provision of Science, Technology, and Innovation projects in Vietnam.
- + Research on the current state of implementing PPP models (according to the Law on Public-Private Partnership Investment) in the field of science, technology, and innovation in Vietnam.
- + Research and analyze the factors affecting the success of PPP models in Vietnam.
- + Research the cooperation mechanisms between the public and private sectors to operate technology and innovation projects in Vietnam.
- + Research and evaluate forms of public-private partnerships, PPP contracts in various fields, and propose selections of PPP forms in technology and innovation projects in Vietnam.
- + Provide suggestion to policymakers to develop solutions that promote PPP models in the provision of technology and innovation projects in Vietnam.
- + Propose solutions to encourage and promote PPP models in the provision of technology and innovation projects in Vietnam.

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

Content 1: Research on the experiences of implementing Public-Private Partnership (PPP) models worldwide in the field of science, technology, and innovation.

- 1.1. Study the mechanisms, policies, and legal frameworks related to public-private partnerships in several countries around the world.
- 1.2. Research the advantages and difficulties in developing public-private partnership models in some countries globally.
- 1.3. Investigate experiences in developing certain public-private partnership models in implementing science, technology, and innovation activities worldwide.

Content 2: Research on the current state of public-private partnership activities and the development of PPP projects in Vietnam.

- 2.1. Study the legal frameworks, mechanisms, and policies related to public-private partnerships in Vietnam.
- 2.2. Analyze some successful PPP models in Vietnam.
- 2.3. Research the difficulties and challenges in implementing public-private partnership activities in Vietnam.
- 2.4. Study development orientations and policies to promote public-private partnership activities in the current period in Vietnam.

Content 3: Research on the status of implementing science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam.

- 3.1. Study practical aspects of existing mechanisms and policies related to implementing science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam.
- 3.2. Research the current state of some models for delivering science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam.
- 3.3. Investigate difficulties and challenges during the implementation of science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam.
- 3.4. Analyze actual needs, opportunities, and trends in implementing science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam.

Content 4: Research on cooperation methods between the public and private sectors to implement science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam.

- 4.1. Study the status and analyze practical needs for developing public-private partnership (PPP) models when implementing science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam.
- 4.2. Analyze barriers and challenges during the implementation of science, technology, and innovation projects in the form of public-private partnerships in Vietnam.
- 4.3. Research and analyze public-private partnership methods suitable for the characteristics of science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam.

Content 5: Propose solutions to encourage and promote public-private partnership (PPP) models in providing science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam.

- 5.1. Propose solutions to improve mechanisms and policies to promote public-private partnership models when implementing science, technology, and innovation projects in Vietnam.
- 5.2. Research methods for evaluating effectiveness and controlling the quality of science, technology, and innovation project implemented through public-private partnerships.
- 5.3. Study methods for developing the market for science, technology, and innovation in the form of public-private partnerships.

METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

Systems Approach: This approach requires researching and evaluating the feasibility of Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) in the provision of science, technology, and innovation services; considering the interactions between internal and external factors, as well as past and present elements. This approach also aids in proposing and offering appropriate and holistic solutions. It is necessary to consider current policies, the readiness level of entities operating in the field of science, technology, and innovation; specific legal systems and differences between countries, draw lessons learned, and propose optimal solutions.

Structural-Functional Approach: The structural-functional approach will identify "problems," more broadly societal issues, corresponding to groups of mechanisms and policies. On this basis, clearly determine the current state of policies, the implementation status of PPP cooperation projects, and the execution of strategies and programs for science and technology development. Investigate causes and results and propose appropriate solutions.

Interdisciplinary Approach: This approach also helps ensure that the research topic can have diverse and objective perspectives, thereby enhancing the value of the research results, especially the recommendations.

Historical Approach: Applying the historical approach will help the research recognize consistent elements with regular patterns. On this basis, it also helps the study clearly identify the requirements to meet objectives. The development process of PPP cooperation policies, changes in social context, and the needs of organizations, businesses, and individuals.

Sustainable Development Approach: Orienting towards a sustainable development approach is extremely important to affirm the feasibility and applicability of policy and mechanism recommendations. To aim for socio-economic sustainable development goals, the research team applies a sustainable development approach and the essential needs of society to have objective and comprehensive insights.

RESEARCH METHODS AND TECHNIQUES USED

+ Statistical Methods, Information Collection, and Document Analysis: The entire system of documents related to this research will be collected, compiled, translated, and systematized.

Based on the classification of relevant documents, the issues that need to be studied within this topic will be extracted. All results collected through the research overview activities will be discussed and shared within the research team and with other scientists through seminars and scientific workshops.

Supplementing and refining will deepen the research issues through learning experiences from abroad and in-depth interviews with experts.

b) In-depth Interview Method: An interview is a conversation conducted according to a certain plan through questions and answers between the interviewer and the informant, based on a prepared questionnaire. Individual in-depth interviews are characterized by exploratory questions and open-ended questions to extract deep information about the realities that need to be studied.

The subjects of in-depth interviews are managers of PPP activities, scientists, team leaders, science and technology management staff of research institutes, universities, and leaders of research and university units.

c) Questionnaire Method: The purpose of this method is to obtain information from respondents on paper by filtering and testing the importance and necessity of pre-prepared content. In some cases, the responses help researchers immediately assess the reality when respondents answer incorrectly or unreasonably on certain issues. When respondents fill out the available questionnaires, the researcher has a basis to pose questions to check the knowledge, attitudes, and skills of the respondents.

In the case of this topic, the questionnaire method is specifically used to collect information, understand the needs, and identify obstacles in implementing PPP policies. Besides, the questionnaire method is also used for some experts, managers, or policy proposers to gather input data serving the research process of policies and mechanisms supporting the development of appropriate research capacity.

d) Analysis, Comparison, and Evaluation Method: Based on the overview results, the analysis, comparison, and evaluation methods will be applied to point out characteristics according to several criteria such as: (1) spatial comparison; (2) temporal comparison; (3) comparison by causes and influencing factors; (4) comparison by policies; (5) comparison by fields of activity, etc. From the results derived from analysis and comparison methods, the research team has a basis to comprehensively evaluate the current situation and related issues, thereby ensuring that the lessons learned, and solution recommendations proposed are appropriate.

e) Forecasting Method: Qualitative Forecasting Method: Based on observations of related factors and opinions about the possible connections of these factors in the future. By scientifically surveying opinions, potential activities that can apply PPP cooperation in providing science, technology, and innovation services in Vietnam can be identified.

+ **Anticipated Difficulties When Conducting Surveys**

- Perception and Attitude of Respondents: The awareness and mindset of the respondents may affect the quality of the data collected.
- Caution and Evasion by Some Respondents: Some participants may be guarded or avoid providing information.
- Sample Representation Limitations: Some typical samples may not fully represent all frequently occurring situations, leading to less accurate evaluations.

+ **Investigation and Survey Methods:**

The research team conducts the following activities:

- **Segmenting target groups for investigation**, including government management agencies, organizations providing science, technology, and innovation services; universities, research institutes, etc.

- **Designing questionnaires** to collect opinions and data on implementation needs, difficulties, and obstacles in deploying PPP cooperative projects in the provision of science, technology, and innovation services.
 - **Collecting feedback**, limitations, difficulties, and barriers in implementing PPP policy mechanisms.
 - **Conducting surveys through questionnaires** to assess the impact of policy mechanisms.
 - **Engaging in discussions** to improve the usability of the tools.
- + **Criteria for Selecting Survey Samples:**
- Based on management subjects and activities: Selecting management units related to PPP; organizations providing science, technology, and innovation services, and related entities.
 - Selecting survey subjects according to the scope of project types and geographical areas.
- + **Survey Locations:**
- Surveys are conducted in all of Vietnam, selecting typical examples based on management levels and regions.
- + **Survey Subjects:**
Total number of samples: ~ **500**, including:
- **Surveys and interviews at specific locations:** 120 samples.
 - **Online surveys** for selected subjects: 360
 - **In-depth interviews with experts:** 30
- + **Content of the Investigation and Survey:**
Investigate through questionnaires and in-depth interviews to clarify the following issues:
1. What is the current progress, difficulties, challenges, and risks in applying PPP in innovation and technology projects in Vietnam?
 2. What are the benefits and values that PPP cooperation brings to technology and innovation project development?
 3. Identify potential science and technology projects that can leverage the advantages of the PPP cooperation model.
 4. What are the most important factors contributing to the successful implementation of PPP cooperative projects in science, technology, and innovation?
 5. Among the PPP cooperation models, which one is most suitable for providing science, technology, and innovation projects (analyze according to potential types)?

FINDINGS

- + Current Status of Implementing Public-Private Partnership Models in Science, Technology, and Innovation Activities in Vietnam. Actual Data, Trends, and Initial Analysis.

- + Proposals to improve the quality and effectiveness of PPP projects in the field of science, technology, and innovation
- + Suggestions to amend and update PPP model policies suitable for the conditions and characteristics of science, technology, and innovation project.

DETAIL FINDINGS

Public-private partnerships in science, technology, and innovation can bring benefits to stakeholders such as the state, public organizations, and the private sector, ensuring common interests for the entire society. In reality, both the public and private sectors have certain relative advantages over the other in carrying out specific tasks related to science, technology, and innovation. For the private sector, the need for public-private partnerships may arise due to specific risk concerns when deploying new technologies or a lack of resources when businesses aim to transform scientific inventions into technological innovations and promote commercialization. Basic scientific research projects can generate a wealth of knowledge and provide a solid foundation for long-term development but require time, funding, and high-level human resources. Moreover, the likelihood of these basic research projects reaching the commercialization stage is quite low. Therefore, many scientific research, technology, and innovation projects cannot bring direct revenue to the private sector. Collaborating with the public sector (research institutes, universities, scientific knowledge systems, teams of highly qualified and experienced scientists, etc.) can help businesses reduce costs, minimize risks, and focus more on commercializing research outcomes. From the state's perspective, the fundamental reason for supporting science and technology is based on the notion of common societal benefits, which exceed the gains businesses achieve from their investments.

Another evident reality is that science, technology, and innovation activities in Vietnam are currently organized and implemented in a very diverse manner through various methods. Many research projects are interdisciplinary, requiring very deep and complex expertise, integrating multiple technologies and new knowledge to produce specific products. Consequently, Vietnamese enterprises find it challenging to participate in large research projects due to insufficient resources, personnel, experience, and necessary information.

According to specific surveys conducted during the research, the team found that businesses consider public-private partnerships necessary for implementing science, technology, and innovation activities. However, private enterprises are concerned about the cooperation model, methods of collaboration, and the delineation of results and benefits from technology research or innovation projects. Many businesses, especially small and medium-sized enterprises in Vietnam, lack teams

of technology and innovation experts and do not have departments or units specializing in research and development or technology management. As a result, these enterprises lack foundational knowledge, information, and experience in developing technological activities and innovation. They do not share a common language with public units in executing research tasks due to differing understandings, implementations, and objectives in deploying technology development and innovation activities compared to the public sector. Particularly, in-depth surveys and interviews reveal a clear lack of trust between the public and private sectors when implementing technology and innovation activities.

Science, technology, and innovation activities in Vietnam are currently governed and influenced by at least six laws related to the science and technology sector, including: the 2013 Law on Science and Technology (29/2013/QH13); the 2017 Law on Technology Transfer (07/2017/QH14); the 2008 Law on High Technology (21/2008/QH12); the 2005 Law on Intellectual Property (50/2005/QH11); the amended 2009 Law on Intellectual Property (36/2009/QH12); the amended 2023 Law on Intellectual Property (07/2022/QH15); the 2011 Law on Measurement (04/2011/QH13); the 2007 Law on Product and Goods Quality (05/2007/QH12); and the amended 2018 Law on Product and Goods Quality (35/2018/QH14). Additionally, public-private partnership (PPP) models in the field of science, technology, and innovation are directly affected by the 2020 Law on Investment under the Public-Private Partnership method (64/2020/QH14); the 2019 Law on Public Investment (39/2019/QH14); the 2015 Law on State Budget (83/2015/QH13); and the 2017 Law on Management and Use of Public Property (15/2017/QH14), among others.... Beneath these laws, there are numerous other current legal documents related to public asset management, investment management, responsibilities of involved parties, evaluation mechanisms, and asset valuation that require attention. Therefore, practical experience shows that when businesses wish to engage in public-private partnership activities in the field of science, technology, and innovation, it is much more challenging than in other fields. Especially given that one of the biggest characteristics of science, technology, and innovation is the level of risk, the lag in impact, and the effectiveness achieved; the results are very difficult to quantify using conventional methods.

Some other detailed findings we can see are:

There are still many obstacles and inadequacies in the current regulations related to major issues such as investment procedures, risk-sharing mechanisms, difficulties in investors' access to credit, as well as the lack of dispute resolution mechanisms...

Specifically, regarding investment procedures, the PPP Law came into effect on January 1, 2021. However, by the end of March 2021, the Government had only issued Decree No. 28/2021/ND-CP stipulating the financial management mecha-

nism for investment projects under the public-private partnership method, and Decree No. 35/2021/ND-CP detailing and guiding the implementation of the PPP Law. Thus, these two decrees were issued nearly three months later than the effective date of the Law. Other guiding documents of the PPP Law were also issued quite slowly.

"The delay in issuing guiding documents is considered the biggest bottleneck currently for the implementation of PPP projects in recent years and in the coming time."

Regarding the risk-sharing mechanism, although the PPP Law has stipulated some measures to ensure investment and share risks in PPP projects, these measures are assessed as not meeting market requirements.

For example, concerning revenue risk-sharing commitments, Article 82 of the PPP Law stipulates the commitment to guarantee minimum revenue for PPP projects in the forms of BOT, BTO, BOO. In cases where, even after adjusting price schedules, fees, and project contract terms, the actual annual revenue is below 75% of the revenue in the financial plan, the State commits to compensate 50% of this shortfall to the enterprise implementing the PPP project.

However, the PPP Law allows this to be done only when "planning, policies, and related laws change, reducing revenue." With this regulation, the State does not share revenue risks due to market factors and demand but only shares in cases where changes in planning and laws reduce revenue.

Additionally, the PPP Law does not have a mechanism to ensure the responsibilities of competent state management agencies in PPP contracts. Meanwhile, the risk for private investors is very high in cases where the contracting agencies fail to fulfill their responsibilities under the contract, leading to financial losses for private investors.

Besides the obstacles and inadequacies in the legal framework, private investors also face many difficulties in accessing credit, hindering their ability to participate in PPP projects.

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

This research can provide extremely valuable reference information on policy mechanisms for public-private partnerships in the fields of science, technology, and innovation in Vietnam.

Policy maps, policy matrices, legal mechanisms, and stakeholders involved in implementing public-private partnerships in the fields of science, technology, and innovation are also clarified.

From an academic perspective, theoretical models of public-private partnerships in science, technology, and innovation will be considered, with specific analyses of stakeholders, responsibilities, and implementation conditions. Correlation models between the responsibilities and benefits of public and private stakeholders participating in public-private partnership activities will also be thoroughly studied. Through the research process, variables and factors that directly impact the likelihood of success for a public-private partnership project in science, technology, and innovation will be specifically analyzed based on various statistical data and survey results. This will allow us to draw conclusions about the key factors that need to be considered and controlled to enhance the success rate of public-private partnerships in the fields of science and technology.

The final and extremely important outcome of this research is the recommendations and policy proposals, providing specific analyses of Vietnam's current policies related to public-private partnerships and the management of science, technology, and innovation activities. These recommendations and policy proposals will help improve quality and increase the number of public-private partnership projects in the fields of science, technology, and innovation.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

Should PPP models be used for science, technology, and innovation projects?

How should the difficulties regarding risks and risk management be considered when implementing PPP projects in the field of technology and innovation?

Issues related to asset valuation, impact assessment of research project results, quality control, and the delineation of intellectual property among stakeholders when participating in public-private projects in the field of technology and innovation.

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